

(0.5 × 0.5 m interplant space) were collected.

For the hybrid program, we are

synthesizing one population for irrigated rice and one for upland rice. The long stigma of the wild

allogamous species *Oryza longistaminata* is being introduced in these populations. □

Cytogenic relationship between two cytoplasmic male-sterile lines

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Cytoplasmic-genetic male sterility (CMS), conditioned by the interaction of nuclear and cytoplasmic factors, is used extensively in hybrid breeding programs for self-pollinated crops. Hybrid varieties grown commercially in China are derived mostly from cytoplasmic sources of wild rice *Oryza sativa* f. *spontanea*, designated as WA (wild rice with aborted anthers). Alternative sources of cytotosterility are needed to protect F₁ hybrids against potential genetic vulnerability to diseases and insects.

We have developed a new CMS (A) line, IR54755A, which has the cytoplasm of land race ARC13829-16 introduced from Assam, India, and the nuclear genotype of elite breeding line IR10179-2-3-1. Another CMS line, IR46828A, was developed in the same nuclear genotype with the WA cytoplasm from Chinese CMS line Zhen Shan 97A. We studied the cytogenic relationship between the two cytotesterile lines developed from the two different cytoplasmic sources.

Each CMS line was crossed with its maintainer and single plant selections of a number of other maintainers,

Pollen fertility behavior of F₁ progenies between CMS, maintainer, and restorer lines. IRRI, 1986 dry season.

Male parent	Female parent											
	IR46828A					IR54755A						
	Plants (no.)	F ₁ plants (no.) in pollen fertility class ^a					Plants (no.)	F ₁ plants (no.) in pollen fertility class				
	CS	S	PS	PF	F		CS	S	PS	PF	F	
IR54755B	19	19	0	0	0	0	48	48	0	0	0	0
IR46828B	49	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	0
IR46829B	9	7	2	0	0	0	10	10	0	0	0	0
IR46830B	8	8	0	0	0	0	10	10	0	0	0	0
IR36R	9	0	0	0	0	9	8	0	0	0	2	6
IR46R	9	0	0	0	0	9	10	0	0	0	0	10
IR64R	6	0	0	0	0	6	10	4	3	1	2	0
IR9761-19-1R	6	0	0	0	0	6	6	0	0	0	1	5
IR28	9	0	0	0	0	9	9	0	2	0	3	4
IR34	5	2	2	1	0	0	10	9	1	0	0	0
IR43	10	6	4	0	0	0	10	5	3	2	0	0
IR52	8	0	0	0	0	8	10	0	0	0	0	10

^a pollen fertility classes: cs = completely sterile, 0% pollen fertility; s = sterile, 1-10% pollen fertility; PS = partially sterile, 11-30% pollen fertility; PF = partially fertile, 31-60% pollen fertility; F = fertile 61-100% pollen fertility.

restorers, and partial restorers of the WA cytotesterility system. The F₁ population of these crosses was evaluated for pollen fertility using 1% IKI solution.

The maintainers of the two CMS lines (IR54755B and IR46828B) effectively maintained the male sterility in the two cytotesterile lines (see table). However, IR64R, IR9761-19-IR, IR28, IR34, and IR43 showed differential fertility in crosses with the two CMS lines.

These results indicate that the cytoplasmic factors inducing male sterility in IR46828A and IR54755A may be different. The maintainers IR46828B and IR54755B, derived from the line IR10179-2-3-1, have genotypes capable of maintaining both cytotesterility systems. The cytogenic differences observed here need to be substantiated by analysis of mitochondrial DNA of the two CMS lines. □

Survival of some F₁ rice hybrids and their parents in saline soil

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Increased vegetative and root vigor are useful traits to use in adapting rice plants to soil and climatic stresses. Usually, F₁ hybrids express these traits. We evaluated 12 F₁ rice hybrids

and their parents for survival in saline soil at IRRI in the 1986 dry season. Although the hybrids' parents are not known to be tolerant of salinity, our objective was to test the usefulness of hybrid vigor under such stresses as soil salinity.

Five-wk-old seedlings grown on wet seedbeds were transplanted at 50 hills/entry in a field where salinity to an EC of 7 dS/m had been induced by

adding common salt. Check varieties were IR28 (salt sensitive) and IR9884-54-3 (salt tolerant). The field salinity level was maintained throughout the experiment. Plant survival was recorded at 6, 12, and 15 wk after transplanting.

Salinity prolonged the growth duration of all varieties tested. Very early parents and hybrids flowered about 100 d after seeding.

Six of the 12 hybrids showed strikingly increased survival compared to their parents (see table). In three cases, hybrids and parents were comparable; in two, hybrids were inferior to the better parent. The hybrid 97A/Milyang 54 showed superiority over the parents at early stages but subsequently became comparable to them.

These results indicate that F_1 hybrids could be superior to their parents in adaptability to salinity. Because the parents of the hybrids tested are not known for salinity tolerance, better performance of some hybrids can be attributed to increased root and shoot vigor.

Survival of some parents (female, male) and their hybrids (F_1) at 6, 12, and 15 wk after transplanting (WAT) in a saline field (EC = 7 dS/m). IRRI, 1986.

Hybrid or variety	Survival (%)								
	6 WAT			12 WAT			15 WAT		
	Female	Male	F_1	Female	Male	F_1	Female	Male	F_1
97A/Milyang 54	26	32	50	16	12	16	16	10	16
IR46830A/IR50	28	58	60	8	46	54	8	40	46
IR46830A/IR9761-19-1	28	26	64	8	14	34	8	8	18
V20A/IR9761-19-1	16	26	28	16	14	18	14	8	12
IR21845/IR29512	28	74	38	18	66	22	14	62	16
IR21845/IR19392	28	48	60	18	44	54	14	44	50
IR21845/IR20933	28	22	44	18	8	40	14	8	34
IR21845/IR14753	28	28	46	18	24	40	14	24	30
IR21845/IR15847	28	22	24	18	16	18	14	12	12
IR21845/IR4422	28	36	32	18	28	24	14	20	12
IR21845/IR13146	28	38	36	18	24	28	14	24	22
IR21845/IR54 R	28	28	46	18	28	46	14	26	40
IR9884-54-3 (resistant check)		93			90			83	
IR28 (susceptible check)		42			40			33	

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

TISSUE CULTURE

Variability in quantitative traits of anther culture-derived progenies

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We studied the pattern of variability in quantitative traits of homozygous lines developed from anther-derived plants of the cross Co 37/Co 40.

Anthers were collected from F_1 plants during 1979 wet season and cultured in the laboratory. Sixteen

plants were established in October 1980. Seven A_1 plants (R1 to R7) resembling the parent (Co 37) in vigor, growth, and seed set were grown individually in A_2 in 1981 wet season (Jun-Sep). They were uniform within each progeny and carried forward as individual lines.

During 1982 wet season, 10 plants were established for each entry, with 3 replications. The F_4 of Co 37/Co 40 and Co 37 alone were included for comparison. Plant height at maturity, number of productive tillers, panicle

length, grains per panicle, and grain yield per plant were measured for each plant.

All the seven lines exhibited variations comparable to that in Co 37. The F_4 population of the cross showed perceptible variation between plants and within lines for all characters. Similar variation was observed in the next generation during 1983 dry season for all the traits except panicle length. Compared to that in the anther-derived lines, variation was high for all traits (see table).

Performance of anther-derived lines at Coimbatore, India, 1983 dry season.

Culture	Plant height (cm)			Tillers (no.)			Panicle length (cm)			Grains/panicle			Grain weight/plant (g)		
	Range	Mean \pm SE	CV	Range	Mean \pm SE	CV	Range	Mean \pm SE	CV	Range	Mean \pm SE	CV	Range	Mean \pm SE	CV
433 A R1	84-98	91.5 \pm 3.9	4.9	6-11	7.9 \pm 1.6	21.4	20.1-27.1	22.6 \pm 28.0	82.7	143-167	153.5 \pm 8.3	5.6	9.0-10.0	9.6 \pm 3.1	3.2
433 A R2	84-92	89.1 \pm 2.6	3.6	5-12	8.7 \pm 2.3	27.1	19.5-23.6	21.6 \pm 13.1	62.7	95-165	130.5 \pm 20.2	15.9	8.2-9.0	8.6 \pm 2.6	3.0
433 A R3	85-98	90.8 \pm 3.7	4.1	5-12	8.3 \pm 2.2	27.4	19.5-24.3	22.4 \pm 11.9	54.7	116-228	169.1 \pm 28.3	17.3	8.1-8.8	8.5 \pm 2.3	2.8
433 A R4	83-95	88.8 \pm 3.2	3.7	5-12	8.2 \pm 1.9	24.0	21.8-24.8	23.5 \pm 9.4	41.6	105-188	138.1 \pm 26.0	19.5	6.3-7.0	6.7 \pm 2.3	3.5
433 A R5	79-95	85.2 \pm 5.5	6.3	7-12	9.7 \pm 1.9	20.2	19.0-23.2	21.8 \pm 10.5	49.8	85-191	131.9 \pm 34.9	27.4	10.2-11.1	10.7 \pm 2.9	2.8
433 A R6	75-96	85.0 \pm 5.5	6.6	7-12	8.9 \pm 1.8	20.8	19.7-24.5	21.5 \pm 13.3	63.9	75-205	122.1 \pm 39.2	33.2	9.2-10.3	9.7 \pm 3.3	3.5
433 A R7	82-94	87.8 \pm 3.6	4.3	6-12	9.2 \pm 1.9	22.2	18.3-23.5	21.1 \pm 14.2	69.8	97-185	141.4 \pm 30.0	21.9	9.0-9.9	9.5 \pm 3.0	3.2
Vaigai (Co 37)	94-119	103.5 \pm 6.4	6.4	5-12	7.9 \pm 2.1	27.9	21.4-24.4	22.7 \pm 12.8	38.3	100-160	129.7 \pm 17.3	14.2	8.4-9.2	8.8 \pm 2.5	2.9
Vaigai/Co 40 (F5)	90-138	116.2 \pm 7.4	7.8	6-12	9.6 \pm 2.1	30.2	20.1-27.2	23.4 \pm 16.2	72.4	77-175	127.7 \pm 27.0	26.8	8.1-13.4	10.6 \pm 5.0	5.7